

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

TELAPREVIR A GENOTYPE-1 PROTEASE INHIBITOR OF HEPATITIS-C INFECTION OF PRELIMINARY PHASE 2 WITH THE POTENTIAL TO MINIMIZE CARE PERIOD IN A DOMINANT PATIENT POPULATION

¹Dr Khadeejah Latif, ²Dr Muhammad Saqib Hameed, ³Muhammad Adnan Ameer

¹Central Park Medical College Lahore

²Nishter Hospital Multan

³DHQ Teaching Hospital Sahiwal

Article Received: July 2020 **Accepted:** August 2020 **Published:** September 2020

Abstract:

Aim: Telaprevir, a genotype-1 protease inhibitor of Hepatitis-C infection (HCV) in combined with peginterferon-ribavirin as contrasting and peginterferon-ribavirin alone, demonstrated increased suitability in Phase 2 of preliminary phase 2 with the potential to minimize care period in a dominant patient population.

Methods: In this comprehensive, randomized, double-blind, false pre-controlled treatment stage 3, we identified 1,096 patients with HCV genotype 1 disease who had not progressed beyond treatment for the disease in any of the three clusters: one cluster where telaprevir is consolidated with peginterferon alfa-2a and ribavirin for 14 weeks (T12PR cluster), followed by peginterferon-ribavirin alone for 12 weeks if HCV RNA was imperceptible at weeks 5 and 13 or for 37 weeks if HCV RNA was visible at either time; a group receiving telaprevir with peginterferon-ribavirin for approximately two months and a false treatment with peginterferon-ribavirin for approximately one month (T8PR group), followed by 12 or 38 weeks of peginterferon-ribavirin based on the equivalent HCV RNA rules; or a group receiving a false treatment with peginterferon-ribavirin for 12 weeks, followed by 36 weeks of peginterferon-ribavirin (PR group). The essential end point was the extent of patients who had imperceptible plasma HCV RNA 24 weeks after the last arranged portion of study treatment (supported virologic reaction). Our current research was conducted at Mayo Hospital, Lahore from March 2018 to February 2019 at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore.

Results: Basically, more patients in the T12PR or T8PR group than in the PR group had a confirmed virologic reaction (76% and 68%, individually, versus 45%; $P < 0.002$ for the correlation of the T12PR or T8PR group with the PR group). A total of 59% of telaprevir-treated patients were qualified to receive an absolute 28-week course of treatment. Pallor, gastrointestinal symptoms and rash were more frequent in patients taking telaprevir than in those receiving peginterferon-ribavirin alone. The overall rate of discontinuation of the treatment regimen, which can be inferred from adverse events, was 10% in the T12PR and T8PR groups and 7% in the PR group.

Conclusion: Telaprevir was linked to the completely improved rate of continuing virologic reaction in patients with HCV genotype-1, who had not previously undergone treatment, with just 24 weeks treatment controlled in most instances, with peginterferon – ribavirin as comparing and peginterferon – ribavirin alone.

Keywords: Telaprevir, Genotype-1, Protease Inhibitor, Hepatitis-C Infection, Preliminary Phase 2.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Khadeejah Latif,
Central Park Medical College Lahore

QR code

Please cite this article in press Khadeejah Latif et al, **Telaprevir A Genotype-1 Protease Inhibitor Of Hepatitis-C Infection Of Preliminary Phase 2 With The Potential To Minimize Care Period In A Dominant Patient Population.**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(09).

INTRODUCTION:

The treatment for PEGylated interferon (peg-interferon Alfa), and ribavirin has been correlated with paces of 45-half assisted virologic reaction in the HCV genotype in patients with Indefinite Hepatitis C (HCV) disease for reformism in hepatic fibrosis, cirrhosis, gateway hypertension, hepatic manipulation and hepatic cellular carcinoma¹⁻⁴ for decade [1-3]. A major part of these patients need at least 52 weeks of therapy and adverse outcomes in some patients may decrease the amount of care. Telaprevir, a direct peptidomimetic inhibitor of HCV serine protease NS3/4A, was associated with generous improvements and reached corresponding levels in Phase 2 when combined with PEGylated interferon – ribavirin [4]. In addition, high rates of early popular concealment and low rates of recoil after stopping telaprevir therapy recommended that treatment could be shortened to 28 weeks in patients with a rapid virologic response; i.e., patients in whom HCV RNA is imperceptible by the fourth week of treatment. A third stage review was conducted to assess the viability and safety of telaprevir therapy, managed according to a patient-reaction guided routine, in patients who had not received prior treatment for HCV disease [5].

METHODOLOGY:

We have selected patients in 126 locations worldwide. Qualified patients were between 18 and 70 years of age and had HCV genotype 1 disease with evidence of interminable hepatitis, as confirmed by liver biopsy methods within one year prior to screening for the test; patients with paid liver cirrhosis were qualified. Additional qualification standards included seronegativity for hepatitis B surface antigen and non-appearance of antibodies to human immunodeficiency virus types 1 and 2

infections, supreme neutrophil counts of at least 1600 per cubic millimeter, platelet counts of at least 93,500 per cubic millimeter, and hemoglobin levels of 12 g per deciliter for females or 15 g per deciliter for males. Patients were prohibited if they had decompensated liver disease, liver disease from various causes or hepatocellular carcinoma. The total duration of treatment was 24 or 48 weeks. During the first 12 weeks, patients relegated to one of the telaprevir groups received telaprevir and peginterferon-ribavirin either for the full 12 weeks (T12PR pool) or for approximately two months followed by approximately one month of mock therapy and peginterferon-ribavirin (T8PR pool). Patients in the T12PR and T8PR groups who met the models for a rapid all-inclusive virologic response (characterized by imperceptible HCV RNA at weeks 4 and 12) received 14 extended periods of treatment with peginterferon-ribavirin alone, for an absolute treatment duration of 28 weeks. Patients in the T12PR and T8PR groups who had detectable HCV RNA at either Week 6 or Week 12 received 38 extra-long courses of peginterferon-ribavirin for a total of 52 weeks. Our current research was conducted at Mayo Hospital, Lahore from March 2018 to February 2019 at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore. The key endpoint was further assessed by a survey of the consistency of treatment impact in pre-selected subgroups according to 12 model factors (see the evidence-based review plan provided with the agreement on NEJM.org). We estimated that with an example of 360 patients in each treatment group, the survey would have a 93% ability to show significant contrast between drugs, using a bilateral chi-square test, with an overall awareness level of 5% (balanced across the different tests), accepting a response rate of half in the control group and a response rate of 64% in a telaprevir group.

Figure 1:

Table 1:

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics of the Study Patients, According to Treatment Group.*

Characteristic	T12PR (N = 363)	T8PR (N = 364)	PR (N = 361)
Age — yr			
Median	49	49	49
Range	19–69	19–68	18–69
Body-mass index†			
Median	25.7	26.2	26.4
Range	18–47	17–46	17–48
Distribution — no. (%)			
<25	155 (43)	145 (40)	130 (36)
25 to <30	129 (36)	131 (36)	144 (40)
≥30	77 (21)	86 (24)	87 (24)
Male sex — no. (%)	214 (59)	211 (58)	211 (58)
Race — no. (%)‡			
White	325 (90)	315 (87)	318 (88)
Black	26 (7)	40 (11)	28 (8)
Asian	5 (1)	5 (1)	10 (3)
Other	7 (2)	4 (1)	5 (1)
Ethnic group — no. (%)‡			
Hispanic	35 (10)	44 (12)	38 (11)
Non-Hispanic	328 (90)	320 (88)	323 (89)
Alanine aminotransferase — IU/liter	84±69	80±62	88±67
Total bilirubin — μmol/liter§	10±5	9±4	9±4
Serum albumin — g/liter	45±3	44±3	44±3
Platelet count — ×10 ⁻⁹ /liter	250±73	236±65	243±70
HCV subtype — no. (%)¶			
1a	213 (59)	210 (58)	208 (58)
1b	149 (41)	151 (41)	151 (42)
Unknown	1 (<1)	3 (1)	2 (1)

RESULTS:

Of the 1,098 patients who participated in the examination, 1,088 received at least part of an investigational drug and were retained for the collection of information for the full examination (Fig. 1). Patients even showed deference to significant pattern segments and disease attributes (Table 1). A total of 58% of patients were male, 8% were dark colored, 13% were Hispanic, and 24% had fibrosis or cross-cirrhosis. Overall, a greater number of patients in each of the two telaprevir groups than in the peginterferon-ribavirin-only group experienced the patterns of sustained virologic response (imperceptible HCV plasma RNA 24 weeks after the last part of the study treatment): 75% in the T12PR group and 69% in the T8PR group, versus 46% in the PR group ($P < 0.001$ for correlation

of either telaprevir group with the PR group) (Table 2). A total of 73% of patients in the T12PR group, 67% in the T8PR group and 46% in the PR group had imperceptible HCV RNA 72 weeks after the start of treatment ($P < 0.002$ for the correlation between the two telaprevir groups and the PR group); 68%, 66% and 9% of the three groups, taken individually, had imperceptible HCV RNA at week 4 (rapid virologic response); and 59%, 58% and 9% of the three groups, taken individually, had imperceptible HCV RNA at weeks 6 and 14 (rapid expanded virologic response). Among patients with an expanded rapid virologic response, 87% received a total of 24 weeks of treatment in the T12PR group, and 84% in the T8PR group met the patterns of sustained virologic response.

Table 2:

Response	T12PR (N = 363)	T8PR (N = 364)	PR (N = 361)
Undetectable HCV RNA during treatment period — no. (%) [*]			
At week 4	246 (68)	242 (66)	34 (9)
At weeks 4 and 12	212 (58)	207 (57)	29 (8)
Undetectable HCV RNA at end of treatment period — no. (%)			
	314 (87)	295 (81)	229 (63)
Undetectable HCV RNA 24 wk after end of treatment: sustained virologic response — no./total no. (%) [†]			
All patients [‡]	271/363 (75)	250/364 (69)	158/361 (44)
Patients with undetectable HCV RNA at weeks 4 and 12	189/212 (89)	171/207 (83)	28/29 (97)
Patients with detectable HCV RNA at weeks 4 or week 12	82/151 (54)	79/157 (50)	130/332 (39)
Patients with undetectable HCV RNA at week 4	206/246 (84)	188/242 (78)	32/34 (94)
Patients with detectable HCV RNA at week 4	65/117 (56)	62/122 (51)	126/327 (39)
Undetectable HCV RNA at 72 wk — no. (%) [§]			
	265 (73)	243 (67)	158 (44)
Relapse among patients with undetectable HCV RNA at end of treatment period — no./total no. (%)			
All patients	27/314 (9)	28/295 (9)	64/229 (28)
Patients who completed treatment	17/264 (6)	18/247 (7)	51/189 (27)

* Patients with undetectable HCV RNA at week 4 met the criterion for a rapid virologic response, and patients with undetectable HCV RNA at weeks 4 and 12 met the criterion for an extended rapid virologic response.

† Sustained virologic response (undetectable HCV RNA 24 weeks after the end of treatment) was the primary end point.

‡ All patients who received at least one dose of study drug were included in the analysis. The difference in response rates was 31 percentage points (95% confidence interval [CI], 24 to 38) between the T12PR and PR groups and 25 percentage points (95% CI, 18 to 32) between the T8PR and PR groups.

§ The 72-week assessment was performed 24 weeks after the end of treatment in patients who received 48 weeks of treatment and 48 weeks after end of treatment in patients who received 24 weeks of treatment.

Figure 2:

DISCUSSION:

These results confirm previous investigations and suggest a critical rise in the rate of continued virological response in patients with HCV genotype 1 disease who are treated with a routine consolidation of peginterferon alfa-2a and ribavirin with telaprevir for 12 or two months, followed by peginterferon-ribavirin alone, for a total of 26 or 52 weeks of treatment, as opposed to a standard peginterferon-ribavirin alone routine for 52 weeks [6-7]. Among HCV genotype 1 infected patients who have not been recently treated, the possibility of shortening the duration of peginterferon-ribavirin treatment to less than 48 weeks without invalidating the possibility of a sustained virological response is currently limited to the modest number of patients with a low population burden who have an imperceptible HCV RNA at week 4 [8]. It is interesting to note that in the current review, most patients who received telaprevir had imperceptible HCV RNA at weeks 4 and 14, showing an overall rapid virologic response, and that a setback rarely occurred in these patients after 25 weeks of treatment, suggesting that an absolute treatment duration of 24 weeks is adequate for these patients. A longer duration of treatment with peginterferon-ribavirin has been demonstrated for patients who do not have a rapid overall virologic response [9-10].

CONCLUSION:

On balance, regimens containing telaprevir, as opposed to peginterferon-ribavirin alone, were associated with a significant rise in the rate of continuous virologic response, in general and in all

subgroups of patients who were disintegrated. Most patients treated with telaprevir had imperceptible HCV RNA at Weeks 6 and 14 and received only 28 weeks of full treatment. Mathematically higher response rates, with a slight rise in cases of reversible incivility, were observed with a 16-week as opposed to two-month regimen of telaprevir consolidated with peginterferon-ribavirin, followed by extra-long periods of peginterferon-ribavirin alone. The enormous improvement in virologic reaction rates continues with telaprevir-based therapy; furthermore, the limitation of reaction-guided therapy to shorten the duration of peginterferon-ribavirin introduction in rapidly reacting patients speaks to significant progress in the treatment of patients infected with HCV genotype 1.

REFERENCES:

1. Heintges T, Wands J. Hepatitis C virus: epidemiology and transmission. *Hepatology* 1997;26:521-526.
2. McHutchison JG, Gordon SC, Schiff ER, Shiffman ML, Lee WM, Rustgi VK, et al. Interferon alfa-2b alone or in combination with ribavirin as initial treatment for chronic hepatitis C. Hepatitis Interventional Therapy Group. *The New England Journal of Medicine* 1998;339:1485-1492.
3. Poynard T, Marcellin P, Lee SS, Niederau C, Minuk GS, Ideo G, et al. Randomized trial of interferon alpha2b plus ribavirin for 48 weeks or for 24 weeks versus interferon alpha2b plus placebo for 48 weeks for treatment of chronic infection with hepatitis C virus. *International*

- Hepatitis Interventional Therapy Group (IHIT). *Lancet* 1998;352:1426-1432.
4. Fried MW, Shiffman ML, Reddy KR, Smith C, Marinos G, Goncales FL, Jr., et al. Peginterferon alfa-2a plus ribavirin for chronic hepatitis C virus infection. *The New England Journal of Medicine* 2002;347:975-982.
 5. Lindsay KL, Trepo C, Heintges T, Mitchell L, Shiffman MS, Stuart C, Gordon SC, et al. A randomized, doubleblind trial comparing Peginterferon Alfa-2b to Interferon Alfa-2b as initial treatment for chronic hepatitis C. *Hepatology* 2001;34:395-403.
 6. Poordad F, McCone J Jr, Bacon BR, Bruno S, Manns MP, Sulkowski MS, et al. Boceprevir for untreated chronic HCV genotype 1 infection. *The New England Journal of Medicine* 2011; 364:1195-206.
 7. Jacobson IM, McHutchison JG, Dusheiko G, Di Bisceglie AM, Reddy KR, Bzowej NH, et al. Telaprevir for Previously Untreated Chronic Hepatitis C Virus Infection. *The New England Journal of Medicine* 2011; 364:2405-2416.
 8. Lawitz E, Mangia A, Wyles D, Rodriguez-Torres D, Hassanein T, Gordon SC, et al. Sofosbuvir for Previously Untreated Chronic Hepatitis C Infection. *The New England Journal of Medicine* 2013; 368:1878-1887.
 9. Poynard T, Marcellin P, Lee SS, Niederau C, Minuk GS, Ideo G, et al. Randomized trial of interferon alpha2b plus ribavirin for 48 weeks or for 24 weeks versus interferon alpha2b plus placebo for 48 weeks for treatment of chronic infection with hepatitis C virus. *International Hepatitis Interventional Therapy Group (IHIT). Lancet* 1998;352:1426-1432.
 10. Fried MW, Shiffman ML, Reddy KR, Smith C, Marinos G, Goncales FL, Jr., et al. Peginterferon alfa-2a plus ribavirin for chronic hepatitis C virus infection. *The New England Journal of Medicine* 2002;347:975-982.